

Title: Biomolecules for NEET and JEE students in One Page

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Abstract

Biomolecules are the organic substances that are necessary for the structure, function, and control of life processes. This overview offers a comprehensive examination of carbohydrates, proteins, nucleic acids, enzymes, vitamins, and hormones, emphasizing their chemical structure, classification, and biological roles. The study combines basic ideas from organic chemistry with biological concepts to show important events including hydrolysis, oxidation, and peptide bond formation. The mind mapping method shows how these macromolecules are connected, which helps people grasp them better and learn more quickly.

Key Words

Biomolecules, Carbohydrates, Proteins, Nucleic acids, Enzymes, Vitamins, Hormones, Mind mapping

Glucose

Preparation:-
 $\text{Sucrose} \xrightarrow{\text{H}^+} \text{Glucose} + \text{Fructose}$
 $\text{starch} + \text{NH}_2\text{O} \longrightarrow \text{Glucose}$

Chemical Properties:-

- $\xrightarrow{\Delta, \text{HI}}$ n-Hexane
- $\xrightarrow{\text{NH}_2\text{OH}}$ Oxime
- $\xrightarrow{\text{Br}_2/\text{water}}$ Gluconic acid
- $\xrightarrow{\text{Acetic anhydride}}$ Glucose penta-acetate

• Cyclic structure of glucose

[α-D(+)-Glucose]
(Fischer formula)

α-D-(+)-Glycopyranose
(Haworth Structure)

MONOSACCHARIDES
 Further hydrolysis is not possible (Simple sugar).
 Ex: Glucose, Fructose, Ribose

OLIGOSACCHARIDES
 Yields two to ten monosaccharides.
 Ex: Sucrose, Maltose, Lactose

POLYSACCHARIDES
 Yields a large number of monosaccharides units.
 Ex: Starch, Cellulose, Glycogen

Starch	Cellulose	Glycogen
Polymer of α-glucose with two components amylose (15-20%) and amylopectin (80-85%)	It is found in plants. It contains β-D-glucose units connected via glycosidic linkage	This is known as animal starch. It is present in liver, muscle and brain. Its structure is similar to amylopectin.

HORMONES
 Molecules that are synthesised by endocrine glands to control and regulate the functioning of specific organs.

- Steroids
- Polypeptides
- Amino Acids

CARBOHYDRATE
 Polyhydroxy aldehyde (aldose) or ketone (ketose) containing at least one chiral center

CARBOHYDRATE

BIOMOLECULES

• Neutral: equal no. of -NH₂ and -COOH group.
 • Basic: more no. of -NH₂ than -COOH group.
 • Acidic: more no. of -COOH than -NH₂ group.

Polymer of α-amino acids that contain -NH₂ and -COOH group

PROTEINS

Classification

ON the basis of Place of Synthesis

- Essential amino acids can be synthesized in the body.
- Non-essential amino acids are synthesized in the body.

ON the basis of Shape

1. Fibrous: fibre like structure
2. Globular Protein.

Denaturation of protein

When a protein in its native form is subjected to physical change, globules unfold, and proteins lose its biological activity.

NUCLEIC ACID

DEOXYRIBONUCLEIC ACID (DNA)

Compound of sugar β-D-2 deoxyribose

Particles of nucleus of the cell responsible for heredity are called chromosomes

- Bases that make up DNA and RNA
- Adenine (A)
 - Guanine (G)
 - Cytosine (C)
 - Thymine (T)
 - Uracil (U)

RIBONUCLEIC ACID (RNA)

Compound of sugar β-D-ribose

Types of RNA: m-RNA, r-RNA, t-RNA

Nucleic acid chain

ENZYME

Globular proteins that are specific to a particular reaction and for a substrate.

Mechanism of enzyme action

Organic compounds required in diet in small amounts to perform specific biological functions for maintenance and growth.

CLASSIFICATION

Water soluble: B group and vitamin C are soluble in water.

Fat soluble: Soluble in fats and oils but insoluble in water (vitamins A, D, E and K)

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